

On Existence and Uniqueness Results for Generalized Katugampola Differential Problem

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Abstract

We investigate fractional differential equations that involve the Hilfer-Katugampola fractional derivative, establishing a connection between these equations and Volterra-type integral equations. By employing Schauder's fixed point theorem, the study demonstrates the existence and uniqueness of solutions under specific conditions. Additionally, the continuous dependence of solutions on the differentiation order is analyzed using Grnwall's inequality. To validate the theoretical findings and showcase the precision of the proposed approach, numerical examples are provided, highlighting its practical applicability.

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1 Introduction

Fractional calculus (FC) extends traditional calculus by generalizing the concepts of differentiation and integration to arbitrary orders, thereby broadening the scope of mathematical modeling. Over time, significant contributions to fractional calculus were made by researchers such as Liouville, Riemann, Caputo, Grnwall, Letnikov, and Weyl, who developed various fractional differ-integral operators [22, 24, 26]. In recent decades, researchers Hilfer, Hadamard, Katugampola, and de Oliveira have advanced this field by introducing generalized fractional operators, thus offering greater flexibility and precision in capturing complex dynamics [2, 3, 5, 20, 21, 23, 27, 29, 30].

The theory of fractional differential equations (FDEs), inspired by the framework of ordinary differential equations (ODEs), has evolved significantly. This development stems from the unique advantages FDEs offer, such as their capability to naturally incorporate initial and boundary conditions, and their applicability in modeling systems with memory effects [6, 7, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 18, 31]. FDEs have found extensive applications across fields including control theory, viscoelasticity, signal processing, and bio-engineering. They are particularly effective in describing phenomena like anomalous diffusion, material damping, and long-range interactions due to their ability to capture hereditary properties [4, 14, 19, 28].

Recent work on FDEs involving the Hilfer-Katugampola fractional derivative has enriched the understanding of global existence, uniqueness, and stability of solutions [8, 9, 17, 25]. This derivative, with its intermediate memory characteristics, bridges classical and generalized fractional derivatives. Researchers have developed rigorous analytical frameworks using tools like fixed-point theory and Volterra-type integral equations, making substantial strides in this domain. Motivated by this we consider the following fractional differential problem (FDP):

$$(1.1) \quad \begin{cases} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t) = f(t, \zeta(t)), & t \in [a, b] \\ \zeta(a) = \zeta_a, \text{ and } \zeta_a^{[n-j]} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta(a) = \zeta_a^{n-j}, & j \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}, \end{cases}$$

where $\zeta_a^{[j]} = \Lambda_a^n = \left(t^{1-\vartheta} \frac{d}{dt}\right)^j \zeta(t)$. With the assumptions:

- (i) $0 < \sigma \notin \mathfrak{N}$, and $[\sigma] = n - 1$.
- (ii) ζ_a and ζ_a^j are fixed real for each $j \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$.
- (iii) $\zeta \in \mathfrak{C}^{n-1} a, b$ such that ${}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t)$ exists and continuous for each $t \in [a, b]$.
- (iv) $f \in \mathfrak{C}([a, b] \times \mathfrak{R})$.

The paper is arranged as follows. Section 2 is dedicated to recalling definitions, properties, remarks and lemmas that are essential for the subsequent analysis. In section 3, we prove the equivalence integral 3.2 and existence of a unique solution to FDE (1.1). Illustrative examples supporting these results are presented in Section 4, followed by the concluding remarks.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [8] The space $X_c^p(a, b)$ ($c \in \mathfrak{R}, p \geq 1$) consists of those real-valued Lebesgue measurable functions ζ on (a, b) for which $\|\zeta\|_{X_c^p} < \infty$, where

$$\|\zeta\|_{X_c^p} = \left(\int_a^b |t^c \zeta(t)|^p \frac{dt}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \quad p \geq 1, \quad \text{and} \quad \|\zeta\|_{X_c^\infty} = \text{ess sup}_{a \leq t \leq b} |t^c \zeta(t)|.$$

In particular, when $c = \frac{1}{p}$, we see that $X_{1/p}^c(a, b) = L_p(a, b)$.

Definition 2.2. [8] We denote by $\mathfrak{C}[a, b]$ a space of continuous functions ζ on $(a, b]$ with the norm

$$\|\zeta\|_{\mathfrak{C}} = \max_{t \in [a, b]} |\zeta(t)|.$$

The weighted space $\mathfrak{C}_{\gamma, \vartheta}[a, b]$, $0 \leq \gamma < 1$, of functions ζ on $(a, b]$ is defined by

$$(2.1) \quad \mathfrak{C}_{\gamma, \vartheta}[a, b] = \{ \zeta : (a, b] \rightarrow \mathfrak{R} : ((t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta)/\vartheta)^\gamma \zeta(t) \in \mathfrak{C}[a, b] \},$$

with the norm

$$\|\zeta\|_{\mathfrak{C}_{\gamma, \vartheta}} = \|((t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta)/\vartheta)^\gamma \zeta(t)\|_{\mathfrak{C}} = \max_{t \in [a, b]} |((t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta)/\vartheta)^\gamma \zeta(t)|,$$

and $\mathfrak{C}_{0, \vartheta}[a, b] = \mathfrak{C}[a, b]$.

Definition 2.3. [9] Let $\Lambda_\vartheta = (t^{\vartheta-1} \frac{d}{dt})$, $0 \leq \eta < 1$. Denote $\mathfrak{C}_{\Lambda_\vartheta, \eta}^n[a, b]$ the Banach space of functions ζ which are continuously differentiable, with Λ_ϑ , on $[a, b]$ upto $(n - 1)$ order and have the derivative $\Lambda_\vartheta^n \zeta$ on $(a, b]$ such that $\Lambda_\vartheta^n \zeta \in \mathfrak{C}_{\eta, \vartheta}[a, b]$:

$$\mathfrak{C}_{\Lambda_\vartheta, \eta}^n[a, b] = \{ \Lambda \vartheta^k \zeta \in \mathfrak{C}[a, b], k = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1, \Lambda \vartheta^n \zeta \in \mathfrak{C}_{\eta, \vartheta}[a, b] \}, \quad n \in \mathfrak{N},$$

with the norm

$$\|\zeta\|_{\mathfrak{C}_{\Lambda_\vartheta, \eta}^n} = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \|\Lambda \vartheta^k \zeta\|_{\mathfrak{C}} + \|\Lambda \vartheta^n \zeta\|_{\mathfrak{C}_{\eta, \vartheta}}, \quad \|\zeta\|_{\mathfrak{C}_{\Lambda_\vartheta}^n} = \sum_{k=0}^n \max_{t \in \Omega} |\Lambda \vartheta^k \zeta(t)|.$$

In particular, for $n = 0$, we have $\mathfrak{C}_{\Lambda_\vartheta, \eta}^0[a, b] = \mathfrak{C}_{\eta, \vartheta}[a, b]$.

Definition 2.4. [20, 21] The generalise fractional integral and derivative of order $0 < \sigma < 1$, and $\vartheta > 0$ are defined, respective by:

$${}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma \zeta(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} \zeta(s) ds$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} {}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^\sigma \zeta(t) &= \Lambda_\vartheta^n {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{n-\sigma} \zeta(t) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \sigma)} \left(t^{1-\vartheta} \frac{d}{dt} \right)^n \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{n-\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} \zeta(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Where $n = [\sigma] + 1$, $\Lambda_\vartheta^n = \left(t^{1-\vartheta} \frac{d}{dt} \right)^n$.

Lemma 2.1. [23] Let $\sigma \in (0, 1)$, $\eta \in [0, 1)$. If $\zeta \in \mathfrak{C}_{\eta, \vartheta}[a, b]$ and ${}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{1-\sigma} \zeta \in \mathfrak{C}_\eta^1[a, b]$, then

$${}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma {}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^\sigma \zeta(t) = \zeta(t) - \frac{{}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{1-\sigma} \zeta(a)}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-1}.$$

Lemma 2.2. [23] Let $t > 0$, then,

$${}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma \left(\frac{x^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\varepsilon-1} = \frac{\Gamma(\varepsilon)}{\Gamma(\varepsilon + \sigma)} \left(\frac{x^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\varepsilon+\sigma-1}$$

and

$${}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^\sigma \left(\frac{x^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\varepsilon-1} = \frac{\Gamma(\varepsilon)}{\Gamma(\varepsilon - \sigma)} \left(\frac{x^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\varepsilon-\sigma-1}.$$

In case, ${}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^\sigma \left(\frac{x^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-1} = 0$.

Lemma 2.3. [10] Let $0 < \sigma < 1$, $0 < a < b < \infty$, $0 \leq \eta < 1$, and $\zeta \in \mathfrak{C}_{\eta, \vartheta}[a, b]$. If $\sigma > \eta$, then ${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t)$ is continuous on $[a, b]$ and

$${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(a) = \lim_{t \rightarrow a^+} \zeta(t) = 0.$$

Definition 2.5. [23] Let $0 < \sigma < 1$ and $0 \leq \delta \leq 1$, then fractional derivative of function ζ with respect to t of order σ with $\vartheta > 0$, is defined by

$${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta}\zeta(t) = {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\delta(1-\sigma)} \left(t^{1-\vartheta} \frac{d}{dt} \right) {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(1-\sigma)}\zeta(t)$$

where $\eta = \sigma + \delta(1 - \sigma)$.

The following properties hold by generalized Hilfer fractional derivatives:

Property 2.1. The operator can be express as:

$${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta}\zeta(t) = {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\delta(1-\sigma)} \Lambda_{\vartheta} {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{1-\eta} = {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\delta(1-\sigma)} {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\eta}\zeta(t), \quad \text{where } \Lambda_{\vartheta} = \left(t^{1-\vartheta} \frac{d}{dt} \right).$$

Property 2.2. Let $0 < \sigma < 1$ and $0 \leq \delta \leq 1$, and $\eta = \sigma + \delta(1 - \sigma)$. If $\zeta \in \mathfrak{C}_{1-\eta}^{\eta}$, then

$${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\eta} {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t) = {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\delta(1-\sigma)}\zeta(t).$$

Property 2.3. Let $0 < \sigma < 1$ and $0 \leq \delta \leq 1$, and $\eta = \sigma + \delta(1 - \sigma)$. If $\zeta \in \mathfrak{C}_{1-\eta}^{\eta}$, then

$${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\eta} {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\eta}\zeta(t) = {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma} {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta}\zeta(t).$$

Property 2.4. Let $\zeta \in L^1(a, b)$. If ${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\delta(1-\sigma)}\zeta$ exists on $L^1(a, b)$, then

$${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t) = {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\delta(1-\sigma)} {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\delta(1-\sigma)}\zeta(t).$$

Property 2.5. If $\zeta \in \mathfrak{C}_{1-\eta}[a, b]$, ${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{1-\delta(1-\sigma)} \in \mathfrak{C}_{1-\eta}^1[a, b]$. Then

$${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t) = \zeta(t).$$

Definition 2.6. Let $0 < \sigma < 1$, $\vartheta \in \mathfrak{R}$, $n = [\sigma] + 1$, $\vartheta > 0$. The Caputo-type fractional derivative of function ζ is defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{\vartheta}_c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t) &= {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{n-\sigma} \Lambda_{\vartheta}^n \zeta(t) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\sigma)} \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^{\vartheta} - s^{\vartheta}}{\vartheta} \right)^{n-\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} \Lambda_{\vartheta}^n \zeta(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 2.4. Let $\sigma, \vartheta \in \mathfrak{R}$ such that $\sigma > 0$ and $\vartheta > 0$. Then,

$${}^{\vartheta}_c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t) = {}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t) - \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{\Lambda_{\vartheta}^j \zeta(a)}{\Gamma(j-\sigma+1)} \left(\frac{t^{\vartheta} - a^{\vartheta}}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-1}$$

Remark 2.1. Caputo-type Katugampola fractional derivative converges to Caputo-type Remann-liouville fractional derivative, when $\vartheta \rightarrow 1$, i.e.

$$\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow 1} {}^{\vartheta}_c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t) = {}_c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\sigma)} \int_a^t (t-s)^{n-\sigma-1} \zeta^{[n]}(s) ds.$$

Remark 2.2. Caputo-type Katugampola fractional derivative converges to Caputo-type Hadamard fractional derivative, when $\vartheta \rightarrow 0^+$, i.e.

$$\lim_{\vartheta \rightarrow 0^+} {}^{\vartheta}_c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t) = {}_c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma}\zeta(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\sigma)} \int_a^t \left(\log \frac{t}{s} \right)^{n-\sigma-1} \left(s \frac{d}{ds} \right)^n \zeta(s) ds.$$

Lemma 2.5. [23] For $\eta \in \mathfrak{R}$, and $\eta > 0$, $0 < \sigma < 1$, $0 \leq \delta \leq 1$. Then,

$${}^{\vartheta}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \left(\frac{t^{\vartheta} - a^{\vartheta}}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-1} = \frac{\Gamma(\eta)}{\Gamma(\eta+\sigma)} \left(\frac{t^{\vartheta} - a^{\vartheta}}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta+\sigma-1}$$

Proof. Applying Definition 2.5, Lemma 2.2 and Property 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t) &= {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{\delta(1-\sigma)} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^\eta \zeta(t) \\ &= {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{\delta(1-\sigma)} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^\eta \zeta(t) \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-1} \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(\eta)}{\Gamma(\eta - \sigma)} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{\eta-\sigma} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-\sigma-1} \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(\eta)}{\Gamma(\eta + \sigma)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta+\sigma-1}. \end{aligned}$$

For $\lambda < n$, we have ${}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^\lambda = 0$. □

Lemma 2.6. [23] *If $\zeta \in \mathfrak{C}^n[a, b]$, $n - 1 < \sigma < n$, and $0 \leq \delta \leq 1$. Then,*

- i. ${}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^\sigma {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t) = \zeta(t) - \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \Lambda_\vartheta^n \zeta(a)$.
- ii. ${}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^\sigma \zeta(t) = \zeta(t)$.

Proof. To prove first part, we use law of induction. In light of Properties 2.1–2.4, splitting the $\Lambda_\vartheta^n = \frac{d}{dt}(\Lambda_\vartheta^{n-1})$ applying integration byparts, we have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^\sigma {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t) &= {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^\sigma {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{\eta-\sigma} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^\eta \zeta(t) \\ &= {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^\sigma {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^\sigma \zeta(t) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta)} \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-1} s^{\vartheta-1} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^\eta \zeta(s) ds \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta)} \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-1} s^{\vartheta-1} \Lambda_\vartheta^n {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{n-\eta} \zeta(s) ds \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - 1)} \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-2} s^{\vartheta-1} \Lambda_\vartheta^{n-1} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{n-\eta} \zeta(s) ds \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-1} \Lambda_\vartheta^{n-1} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{n-\eta} \zeta(a) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - 2)} \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-3} s^{\vartheta-1} \Lambda_\vartheta^{n-2} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{n-\eta} \zeta(s) ds \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-1} \Lambda_\vartheta^{n-1} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{n-\eta} \zeta(a) - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - 1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-2} \Lambda_\vartheta^{n-2} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{n-\eta} \zeta(a) \\ &\quad \vdots \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - n)} \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-n-1} s^{\vartheta-1} \Lambda_\vartheta^0 {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{n-\eta} \zeta(s) ds \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-1} \Lambda_\vartheta^{n-1} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{n-\eta} \zeta(a) - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - 1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-2} \Lambda_\vartheta^{n-2} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{n-\eta} \zeta(a) \\ &\quad - \dots - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - j + 1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \Lambda_\vartheta^{n-j} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{n-\eta} \zeta(a) \\ &= \zeta(t) - \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \Lambda_\vartheta^n \zeta(a). \end{aligned}$$

Hence first case is completed. For second, we have

$${}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^\sigma \zeta(t) = {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{J}_{a^+}^{\eta-\sigma} {}^\vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^{\eta-\sigma} \zeta(t).$$

In the light of 2.2 with first case above, we come to the desired result. □

Lemma 2.7. [1, 6] (Gronwall's lemma) Let p, q , be two integrable functions and ζ is continuous on $[a, b]$. Assume that p and q are nonnegative and nondecreasing. If

$$p(t) \leq q(t) + \zeta(t) \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-i} p(s) ds,$$

then, for all $t \in [a, b]$, we have

$$(2.2) \quad p(t) \leq q(t) + \int_a^t \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{[\vartheta^{1-\sigma} \zeta(t) \Gamma(\sigma)]^k}{\Gamma(\sigma k)} s^{\vartheta-1} (t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta) q(s) ds.$$

Also, if q is a nondecreasing function on $[a, b]$, then

$$p(t) \leq q(t) E_\sigma \left[\zeta(t) \Gamma(\sigma) \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^\sigma \right].$$

3 Existence and Uniqueness results

We prove the equivalent integral of problem (1.1) in the following lemma.

Lemma 3.1. Let $\zeta \in \mathcal{C}^{n-1}[a, b]$, ζ satisfies (1.1) iff holds the equivalence with:

$$(3.1) \quad \zeta(t) = {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma f(t, \zeta(t)) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - j + 1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \zeta_a^{n-j}.$$

Proof. Let $\zeta \in \mathcal{C}^{n-1}[a, b]$ satisfies (1.1). Using ${}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma$ on both side of (1.1).

$$(3.2) \quad {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma {}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t) = {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma f(t, \zeta(t)).$$

By Theorem 2.6 and intial conditions, we get

$$(3.3) \quad {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma {}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t) = \zeta(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - j + 1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \zeta_a^{n-j}.$$

From equation (3.2) and (3.3), we get (3.1). Conversely, suppose (3.1) holds. Applying ${}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta}$ on both sides of (3.1), we obtain

$${}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t) = {}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma f(t, \zeta(t)) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - j + 1)} {}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \zeta_a^{n-j}.$$

Since, ${}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^j = 0$, for $j = \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$, using Theorem 2.6 we obtain ${}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t) = f(t, \zeta(t))$.

To prove the initial conditions from (3.1). Clearly $\zeta(a) = \zeta_a$.

For $j = n-1$

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_a^{[n-j]} {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta(t) &= \zeta_a^{[1]} {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta(t) \\ &= \left(t^{1-\vartheta} \frac{d}{dt} \right) {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta(t), \end{aligned}$$

using (3.1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta(t) &= {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma+(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} f(t, \zeta(t)) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - j + 1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta_a^{n-j} \\ &= {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma+(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} f(t, \zeta(t)) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - j + 1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \\ &\quad \times \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\eta)} \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{n-\eta-1} s^{\vartheta-1} \zeta_a^{n-j} ds \\ &= {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{n-\delta(n-\sigma)} f(t, \zeta(t)) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta - j + 1)} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\eta+j)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{n-j} \zeta_a^{n-j}. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$t^{1-\vartheta} \frac{d}{dt} \left({}^{\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta(t) \right) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\delta(n-\sigma)-1)} \left(t^{1-\vartheta} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{(n-\delta(n-\sigma)-2)} f(s, \zeta(s)) \right) ds + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \frac{(n-j)}{\Gamma(n-\eta+1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{n-j-1} \zeta_a^{n-j}.$$

Thus

$$\zeta_\vartheta^{[1]\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta(a) = \zeta_a^{[1]}.$$

Repeating the same argument for $j = 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_\vartheta^{[n-1]\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta(t) &= t^{1-\vartheta} (\Lambda_\vartheta^{[n-1]\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta(t))' \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma\delta - n\delta + 1)} \left(t^{1-\vartheta} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{(\sigma\delta - n\delta)} f(s, \zeta(s)) \right) ds + \zeta_a^{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

By the f is continuous on $[a, b]$, we get

$$\left| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma\delta - n\delta + 1)} \left(t^{1-\vartheta} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{(\sigma\delta - n\delta)} f(s, \zeta(s)) \right) ds \right| \leq \|f\| \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{(\sigma\delta - n\delta + 1)},$$

which vanish for $t = a$. Hence $\Lambda_\vartheta^{[n-1]\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(1-\delta)(n-\sigma)} \zeta(t) = \zeta_a^{n-1}$. □

Theorem 3.1. Let f, g be continuous on $[a, b] \times \mathfrak{R}$, and ζ, χ be defined on $\mathfrak{C}^{n-1}([a, b], \mathfrak{R})$ satisfy (1.1). Consider

(i) a real positive K exists, which holding

$$\|\chi(t, s_1) - \chi(t, s_2)\| \leq K \|s_1 - s_2\|$$

$t \in [a, b], \forall s_1, s_2 \in \mathfrak{R}$.

(ii) a function $\Psi \in \mathfrak{C}[a, b]$ exists, which is positively holding

$$\|f(f, \zeta(t)) - g(t, \chi(t))\| \leq \Psi(t) \forall t \in [a, b].$$

Then $\forall t \in [a, b]$ we have

$$(3.4) \quad \|\zeta(t) - \chi(t)\| \leq h(t) + \int_a^t \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{K^j}{\Gamma(j\sigma)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{K\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} h(s) ds,$$

where h is real function on $[a, b]$ defined by:

$$h(t) = {}^{\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma} \Psi(t) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \|\zeta_a^{n-j} - \chi_a^{n-j}\|.$$

Proof. Since ζ and χ are solution of (1.1), therefore

$$(3.5) \quad \zeta(t) = {}^{\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma} f(t, \zeta(t)) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \zeta_a^{n-j}$$

and

$$(3.6) \quad \chi(t) = {}^{\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma} f(t, \chi(t)) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \chi_a^{n-j}.$$

Define: $\Phi(t) = \|\zeta(t) - \chi(t)\|$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(t) &\leq {}^{\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma} \|f(t, \zeta(t)) - g(t, \chi(t))\| + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \|\zeta_a^{n-j} - \chi_a^{n-j}\| \\ &\leq {}^{\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma} \|f(t, \zeta(t)) - g(t, \zeta(t))\| + {}^{\vartheta} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\sigma} \|g(t, \zeta(t)) - g(t, \chi(t))\| \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \|\zeta_a^{n-j} - \chi_a^{n-j}\| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma \Psi(t) + K {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma \|\zeta(t) - \chi(t)\| + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\eta-j} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \|\zeta_a^{n-j} - \chi_a^{n-j}\| \\ &\leq h(t) + \frac{K}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} \Phi(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

By applying Gronwall Lemma 2.7, we come at

$$\Phi(t) \leq h(t) + \int_a^t \sum_{j=1}^\infty \frac{K^j}{\Gamma(j\sigma)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{j\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} h(s) ds.$$

□

Theorem 3.2. *Let f is defined as in (1.1). If a positive constant K exists satisfying*

$$\|f(t, \zeta(t)) - f(t, \chi(t))\| \leq K \|\zeta(t) - \chi(t)\| \quad \forall t \in [a, b], \zeta, \chi \in \mathfrak{X}.$$

Then (1.1) assures a solution on $[a, a + \epsilon]$, where $\epsilon > 0$, is unique.

Proof. Let $X = \{\zeta \in \mathfrak{C}^{n-1}[a, a + \epsilon], {}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t)$ is continuous on $[a, a + \epsilon]\}$.

Define: $\epsilon > 0$ such that $a + \epsilon \leq b$ satisfies:

$$\frac{K}{\Gamma(\sigma + 1)} \left(\frac{(a + \epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^\sigma < 1.$$

Also, $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that

$$(3.7) \quad T(\zeta(t)) = {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma f(t, \zeta(t)) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\eta-j} \zeta_a^{n-j}.$$

Since $\zeta \in X$, clearly $T(\zeta) \in \mathfrak{C}^{n-1}[a, a + \epsilon]$. Applying ${}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^\sigma$ on both side of (3.7) and using Theorem 2.5 and Theorem 2.6, we get

$$\begin{aligned} {}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^\sigma T(\zeta(t)) &= {}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^\sigma {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma f(t, \zeta(t)) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{\zeta_a^{n-j}}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} {}^\vartheta \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^\sigma \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\eta-j} \\ &= f(t, \zeta(t)). \end{aligned}$$

Since, f is continuous in $[a, a + \epsilon]$, then $T(\zeta(t)) \in X$, therefore T is well defined. For $\zeta, \chi \in T$ and $t \in [a, a + h]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|T(\zeta(t)) - T(\chi(t))\| &= \max_{t \in [a, a+h]} |T(\zeta(t)) - T(\chi(t))| \\ &\leq \max_{t \in [a, a+h]} |{}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma f(t, \zeta(t)) - {}^\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\sigma f(t, \chi(t))| \\ &\leq \frac{K}{\Gamma(\sigma + 1)} \left(\frac{(a + \epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^\sigma \|\zeta(t) - \chi(t)\|, \end{aligned}$$

hence X is contraction. Using Theorem 3.1 and Banach fixed point theorem we conclude that X has fixed point and by Theorem 3.1, FDE (1.1) has unique solution on $[a, a + h]$. □

Theorem 3.3. *Let f be defined by (1.1) satisfies Lipschitz condition on second variable, then FDP (1.1) has guarantee a unique solution on $[a, b]$.*

Proof. Consider $t_1 \in (a, b)$ satisfying (3.1) and $t_1 = a + \epsilon$.

Clearly

$$\frac{K}{\Gamma(\sigma + 1)} \left(\frac{t_1^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^\sigma < 1.$$

By deduction of Theorem 3.2, we deduce that (1.1) has unique solution ζ_1 on $[a, t_1]$. Using Theorem 3.1 the solution must satisfies

$$\zeta(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_a^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} f(s, \zeta(s)) ds + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\eta-j} \zeta_a^{n-j}.$$

Denote: $\zeta_a = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\eta-j} \zeta_a^{n-j}$. We gate

$$\zeta(t) = \zeta_a + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_a^{t_1} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} f(s, \zeta(s)) ds + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_{t_1}^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} f(s, \zeta(s)) ds.$$

Where $\zeta_a^1 = \zeta_a + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_a^{t_1} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} f(s, \zeta(s)) ds$. Now, choosing $t_2 \in (t, b)$ such that

$$\frac{K}{\Gamma(\sigma+1)} \left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - t_1^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^\sigma < 1$$

and follows the steps of proof of Theorem 3.2, we conclude that (1.1) has unique solution ζ^2 on $[t_1, t_2]$. Repeating the same argument on interval $[t_{k-1}, t_k]$, for each $k = 1, \dots, c$ where $a = t_0 < t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_c = b$. Thus problem (1.1) has a unique piecewise continuous solution. \square

Theorem 3.4. Let f satisfies the condition of (1.1). If there exists constants $k_1, k_2 > 0$ satisfying

$$(3.8) \quad |f(t, \zeta(t))| \leq k_1 + k_2|\zeta|, \quad \forall t \in [a, b] \quad \zeta \in \mathfrak{R}.$$

Then problem (1.1) has at least one solution on $[a, a + \epsilon] \subset [a, b]$ for some $\epsilon > 0$.

Proof. Let for $\epsilon > 0$ such that $a + \epsilon \leq b$,

$$1 - \frac{k_2}{\Gamma(\sigma+1)} \left(\frac{(a+\epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^\sigma > 0.$$

and the mapping is defined as (3.7), the proof of theorem is in several steps.

Step-I: T is continuous. Let ζ_n be sequence in X . We have

$$(3.9) \quad \begin{aligned} \|T(\zeta(t_n)) - T(\zeta(t))\| &= \max_{t \in [a, a+h]} |T(\zeta(t_n)) - T(\zeta(t))| \\ &\leq \max_{t \in [a, a+h]} |\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\sigma f(t, \zeta(t_n)) - \vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\sigma f(t, \zeta(t))| \\ &\leq \max_{t \in [a, a+h]} |f(t, \zeta(t_n)) - f(t, \zeta(t))| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma+1)} \left(\frac{(a+\epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^\sigma \end{aligned}$$

Since $f \in \mathfrak{C}([a, b] \times \mathfrak{R})$, $\zeta_n \rightarrow \zeta$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Hence T is continuous.

Step-II: T is uniformly bounded.

Let r be a positive constant and $\zeta \in \mathfrak{B}_r := \{\zeta \in X \mid \|\zeta\| \leq r\}$. Using (3.8) we get

$$(3.10) \quad \begin{aligned} |f(t, \zeta(t))| &\leq k_1 + k_2\|\zeta\| \\ &\leq k_1 + k_2r, \quad \forall t \in [a, a + \epsilon]. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$(3.11) \quad \|T(\zeta(t))\| \leq \frac{k_1 + k_2r}{\Gamma(\sigma+1)} \left(\frac{(a+\epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^\sigma + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{|\zeta_a^{n-j}|}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\frac{(a+\epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\eta-j} = r'$$

Therefore, for each $r > 0$ and $\zeta \in \mathfrak{B}_r$, implies $\exists r'$ independent of ζ and t , such that $\|T(\zeta(t))\| \leq r'$, implying T mapping bounded sets into bounded sets in X . Thus T is uniformly bounded.

Step-III: T is equicontinuous.

Consider $t_1, t_2 \in [a, a + \epsilon]$ and $t_1 < t_2$. Define

$$\text{sgn}(a) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \sigma > 1, \\ -1 & \text{if } 0 < \sigma < 1. \end{cases}$$

For all $\zeta \in \mathfrak{B}_r$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |T(\zeta(t_2)) - T(\zeta(t_1))| &\leq |\vartheta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\sigma \left(f(t_2, \zeta(t_2)) - f(t_2, \zeta(t_1)) \right)| \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{|\zeta_a^{n-j}|}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\eta-j} - \left(\frac{t_1^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta}\right)^{\eta-j} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \left| \int_a^{t_2} \left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} f(s, \zeta(s)) ds - \int_a^{t_1} \left(\frac{t_1^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-1} s^{\vartheta-1} f(s, \zeta(s)) ds \right| \\ &+ \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{|\zeta_a^{n-j}|}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} - \left(\frac{t_1^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \right) \\ &\leq \frac{k_1 + k_2 r}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \left[\int_a^{t_1} \text{sgn}(\sigma) s^{\vartheta-1} \left(\left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-1} - \left(\frac{t_1^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-1} \right) ds \right. \\ &+ \left. \int_{t_1}^{t_2} s^{\vartheta-1} \left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-1} ds \right] + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{|\zeta_a^{n-j}|}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} - \left(\frac{t_1^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \right) \\ &\leq \frac{k_1 + k_2 r}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \left[\text{sgn}(\sigma) \left(\left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^\sigma - \left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - t_1^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^\sigma - \left(\frac{t_1^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^\sigma \right) + \left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - t_1^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^\sigma \right] \\ &+ \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{|\zeta_a^{n-j}|}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\left(\frac{t_2^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} - \left(\frac{t_1^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \right) \end{aligned}$$

which tends to 0 as $t_2 \rightarrow t_1$. Thus $T(\zeta(t_2)) \rightarrow T(\zeta(t_1))$. Therefore T maps bounded set into equicontinuous set in X .

Step-IV: T is bounded.

Let $T = \{\zeta \in X\}$ such that $\zeta = \lambda T(\zeta(t))$, $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ is bounded. Let $\zeta \in T$, there exist $\lambda \in (0, 1)$, $t \in [a, a + \epsilon]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\zeta\| &\leq \|T(\zeta(t))\| \\ &\leq \frac{k_1 + k_2 \|\zeta\|}{\Gamma(\sigma + 1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^\sigma + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{|\zeta_n^{n-j}|}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j} \\ &\leq \frac{k_1 + k_2 \|\zeta\|}{\Gamma(\sigma + 1)} \left(\frac{(a + \epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^\sigma + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{|\zeta_n^{n-j}|}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\frac{(a + \epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\zeta(t) \leq \frac{\frac{k_1 + k_2 \|\zeta\|}{\Gamma(\sigma + 1)} \left(\frac{(a + \epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^\sigma + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{|\zeta_n^{n-j}|}{\Gamma(\eta-j+1)} \left(\frac{(a + \epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\eta-j}}{1 - \frac{k_2}{\Gamma(\sigma + 1)} \left(\frac{(a + \epsilon)^\vartheta - a^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^\sigma}.$$

By Step-I to Step-III and Ascoli-Arzela Lemma, $T(\mathfrak{B}_r)$ is included in compact set, therefore T is completely continuous. By Step-IV and Schaefer fixed point theorem, T has fixed point. Hence, from Theorem 3.1 and (3.7), problem (1.1) has at least on solution in $[a, a + \epsilon]$. \square

4 Examples

Example 4.1. Consider the FDE of poulation dynamics model:

$$(4.1) \quad \begin{cases} \vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t) = f(t, \zeta(t)), & \zeta(0) = \zeta_0 \end{cases}$$

where,

$$f(t, \zeta(t)) = r\zeta(t) \left(1 - \frac{\zeta(t)}{k} \right) + \cos(t), \quad \zeta(0) = \zeta_0.$$

Its equivalent integralis:

$$\zeta(t) = \zeta_0 + \frac{r}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \left(\frac{t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^{\sigma-1} \left(\zeta(s) \left(1 - \frac{\zeta(s)}{k} \right) + \cos(s) \right) ds$$

For $r = 0.5$, $k = 1.5$, $\zeta_0 = 0.1$, $\sigma = \{0.5, 0.65, 0.8, 0.9, 0.95\}$, $\delta = 0, 0.5, 1$.

Following particular solutions to (4.1) are simulated for parameters given in Tables 4.1 and 4.2 (which corresponds to Figures 4.1 (a)-(b), and 4.2(a)).

Case-I: Hilfre fractional equivalent integral :

$$\zeta(t) = \zeta_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\delta(1 - \sigma))} \int_0^t (t - s)^{\delta(1 - \sigma) - 1} (r\zeta(s) \left(1 - \frac{\zeta(s)}{k} \right) + \cos(s)) ds.$$

Case-II: Katugampola fractional equivalent integral.

$$\zeta(t) = \zeta_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t (t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta)^{\sigma-1} (r\zeta(s) \left(1 - \frac{\zeta(s)}{k}\right) + \cos(s)) ds.$$

Case-III: Caputo fractional equivalent integral.

$$\zeta(t) = \zeta_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\sigma-1} (r\zeta(s) \left(1 - \frac{\zeta(s)}{k}\right) + \cos(s)) ds.$$

Example 4.2. Consider the FDE of logistic growth:

$$(4.2) \quad \begin{cases} \vartheta \mathfrak{D}_{a^+}^{\sigma, \delta} \zeta(t) = f(t, \zeta(t)) & \zeta(0) = \zeta_0 \end{cases}$$

where,

$$f(t, \zeta(t)) = -k\zeta(t)(1 - \zeta(t)) + \sin(t), \quad \zeta(0) = \zeta_0.$$

For $k = 1, \zeta(0) = 0.2, \delta = 0, 0.5, 1; \sigma \in \{0.5, 0.65, 0.8, 0.9, 0.95\}$.

Following particular solutions to (4.2) are simulated for parameters given in Tables 4.1 and 4.3 (which corresponds to Figures 4.2 (b), and 4.3 (a)-(b)).

Case-I: Involving Hilfer fractional derivative:

$$\zeta(t) = \zeta_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\delta(1-\sigma))} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\delta(1-\sigma)-1} (-k\zeta(s)(1 - \zeta(s)) + \sin(s)) ds.$$

Case-II: Katugampola fractional equivalent integral.

$$\zeta(t) = \zeta_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t (t^\vartheta - s^\vartheta)^{\sigma-1} (-k\zeta(s)(1 - \zeta(s)) + \sin(s)) ds.$$

Case-III: Caputo fractional equivalent integral.

$$\zeta(t) = \zeta_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\sigma-1} (-k\zeta(s)(1 - \zeta(s)) + \sin(s)) ds.$$

Parameter	Value / Description
k	1.0 (Logistic growth rate)
r	0.5 (Population growth rate)
K	1.5 (Carrying capacity)
y_0 (Logistic Growth)	0.2 (Initial value)
y_0 (Population Dynamics)	0.1 (Initial value)
σ	{0.5, 0.65, 0.8, 0.9, 0.95} (Fractional order)
δ	{0, 0.5, 1} (Hilfer parameter)

Table 4.1: Parametric Values for Logistic Growth and Population Dynamics

t	Hilfer ($\delta = 0$)	Hilfer ($\delta = 0.5$)	Hilfer ($\delta = 1$)	Katugampola	Caputo
0.00	0.1000	0.1000	0.1000	0.1000	0.1000
0.10	0.1010	0.1011	0.1012	0.1011	0.1010
0.20	0.1039	0.1040	0.1041	0.1040	0.1039
0.30	0.1084	0.1085	0.1086	0.1085	0.1084
0.40	0.1144	0.1146	0.1147	0.1145	0.1144
0.50	0.1218	0.1220	0.1222	0.1219	0.1218

Table 4.2: Results for Population Dynamics ($\delta = 0, 0.5, 1$ and $\sigma = \{0.5, 0.65, 0.8, 0.9, 0.95\}$)

Figure 4.1: Logistic Growth for different δ values.

Figure 4.2: Logistic Growth for $\delta = 1$ and Population Dynamics for $\delta = 0$.

Figure 4.3: Logistic Growth for different δ values.

t	Hilfer ($\delta = 0$)	Hilfer ($\delta = 0.5$)	Hilfer ($\delta = 1$)	Katugampola	Caputo
0.00	0.2000	0.2000	0.2000	0.2000	0.2000
0.10	0.2015	0.2016	0.2017	0.2016	0.2015
0.20	0.2072	0.2073	0.2075	0.2073	0.2072
0.30	0.2151	0.2153	0.2154	0.2152	0.2151
0.40	0.2254	0.2256	0.2258	0.2255	0.2254
0.50	0.2380	0.2382	0.2384	0.2381	0.2380

Table 4.3: Results for Logistic Growth ($\delta = 0, 0.5, 1$ and $\sigma = \{0.5, 0.65, 0.8, 0.9, 0.95\}$)

5 Conclusions and Future Scope:

This study establishes a robust theoretical framework for fractional differential equations involving the Hilfer-Katugampola fractional derivative, bridging these equations with Volterra-type integral equations. The existence and uniqueness of solutions are rigorously proven using Schauder's fixed point theorem, while Gronwall's inequality is employed to analyze the continuous dependence of solutions on the order of differentiation. Theoretical results are further supported through applications to logistic growth and population dynamics models, demonstrating the practical relevance and reliability of the proposed approach. Numerical examples validate the effectiveness and accuracy of the methodology, reinforcing its potential for solving real-world problems.

In future work, the proposed framework can be extended to more complex systems, including stochastic fractional models and multi-dimensional scenarios. Furthermore, exploring computational techniques for large-scale simulations and real-world applications in biology, ecology, and engineering will broaden the scope and utility of this study.

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